

REPOPSI Final Project Report

Project Title

TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs

Project Duration

October 2022 – July 2023 (nine months)

Report Submission

The final report was submitted on July 31, 2023 via the EOSC Future Funding platform using the provided template.

About the Project

[REPOPSI](#) is an open digital repository for Open Access psychological scales, tests, and other research instruments translated into Serbian or developed by Serbian scientists.

More about the REPOPSI improvement project can be found at:

[EOSC Future grant: REPOPSI](#) on the RDA website

[How did we get to REPOPSI 2.0? The project that improved the Repository in a nutshell](#) on the REPOPSI website

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This report was created as part of the project titled “TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs”, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536. The project has received support from the [EOSC Future](#) through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#), based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

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1. Project summary and milestones/tasks/deliverables that have been completed

Please list with bullets your achievements to date. Please add references for each bullet, ideally PIDs, if not available URLs (of your presentations, datasets, publications, etc.). *

REPOPSI is an open repository that enables users to freely access and share psychological instruments (such as scales, questionnaires, and tests) in Serbian and other languages. By implementing EOSC and RDA recommendations and resources, this project improved REPOPSI's adherence to TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology) and FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reuse) principles.

Work Package 1 (WP1) was focused on building the technologies needed to improve REPOPSI's adherence especially to the principles of User Focus, Sustainability, Findability, and Interoperability. To get a better idea on where to concentrate our efforts and to evaluate the progress we made, we conducted a self-assessment test at the start and at the end of the project.

WP1 achievements to date are:

- REPOPSI Start-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535024>
- REPOPSI Preliminary Start-Project Evaluation Using the CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535053>
- REPOPSI website, available in both Serbian and English
<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>
- The preparation of REPOPSI Terms of Use:
<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/terms-of-use/>
- The preparation of REPOPSI Privacy Policy:
<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/privacy-policy/>
- REPOPSI online contribution form, available in both Serbian and English
<https://www.soscisurvey.de/repopsi/> (also accessible from the website at <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>)
- An interactive, open-source app in English for searching REPOPSI metadata
<https://repopsi.shinyapps.io/repopsi/> (also accessible from the website at <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-search-repopsi/>)
- Open code to reproduce the REPOPSI search app
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7934950>
- Slides from an online training session on the development and maintenance of the REPOPSI search app <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7934971>

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- REPOPSI Metadata Enricher: Open Python script for generating XML metadata documents for the Repository records, in compliance with the latest version of the DataCite Metadata Schema <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8150869>
- A Report on Piloting the Application of a Controlled Vocabulary to an OSF-Hosted Repository: The Case of REPOPSI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8178798>
- XML metadata documents were generated for 171 instruments currently available in full in REPOPSI and manually deposited into their respective components (i.e. folders) on Open Science Framework (OSF) platform. All of the OSF components can be accessed from the OSF project at <https://osf.io/5zb8p/>. An example of an OSF component with a metadata document (Metadata_BDR.xml) can be viewed at <https://osf.io/zd6up/>.
- REPOPSI Maintenance Manual and Workflow, available Open Access and updated to reflect the improvements made during the project <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8195982>
- REPOPSI End-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8189262>
- REPOPSI End-Project Evaluation Using the CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8200102>

Work Package 2 (WP2) was focused on communicating the results of the project, advertising REPOPSI to a wider user base, and promoting further uptake of EOSC and RDA resources.

WP2 achievements to date are:

- Opening all of the project outputs in a designated Zenodo community <https://zenodo.org/communities/repopsi-rda/>
- Lightning talk for the RDA/EOSC Future Satellite Event "Building blocks of Global Research Commons: Europe and beyond" at the Research Data Alliance 20th Plenary Meeting <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7787007>
- Invited presentation at the Open Science Days IV, 3-4 November, 2022, Belgrade (Serbia) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7425349>
- Active promotion of project outputs on social media in both English and Serbian, primarily via our Laboratory's social media accounts on Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn, but also via our personal accounts (e.g. on Mastodon). Please find all of the social posts URLs under 4. Other Outreach activities/events.
- Writing blog posts on Repository development and EOSC and RDA adoption and publishing them on the REPOPSI website at <https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/blog/>
- Submission of the EOSC in Practice Story (to be available at) <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-in-practice/stories>
- Organizing a local online workshop to share lessons learned <https://zenodo.org/record/8071879>

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- Registering the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philosophy as an EOSC Provider to the EOSC Portal <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/providers/eosc.ubfzf>
- Registering REPOPSI as a new Resource in the EOSC Portal <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/eosc.ubfzf.reposi>
- Updating the REPOPSI re3data entry to reflect the improvements made during the project <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013441>
- Adding REPOPSI to the FAIRsharing.org Registry <https://fairsharing.org/4918>

Work Package 3 (WP3) was focused on increasing the number of REPOPSI records.

WP3 achievements to date are:

- Recruiting three psychology master’s students from the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philosophy (the students are introduced at <https://www.reposi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/reposi-project/>, “WP3: Improving the completeness of the data in the Repository” subheading)
- Training the student assistants <https://zenodo.org/record/7789062>
- Student assistants searching the E-theses repository, documenting doctoral theses, and then retrieving and documenting 120 new original psychological instruments and instrument translations from the theses, suitable to be recorded in REPOPSI. Fifteen of those instruments were added to REPOPSI in July 2023, bringing the Repository to a total of 200 records. (It can be seen from the OSF Wiki that in June 2023 the total number of records was 185: <https://osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/home/?view=180&menu>. The latest version of the OSF Wiki states that this number is 200: <https://osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/home/>.)

2. EOSC Relevant Interactions and Outputs

Did you use one or several of the services provided by the [EOSC marketplace](#)? These might be services which only recently were onboarded into the EOSC marketplace, please check.

LIST with bullets the used EOSC services here (please provide links). *

- FAIRsharing: https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/eosc.oxford_e-research_centre.21697de1a5b10b8eb5fad857edecf5c9
- re3data - registry of research data repositories: https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/eosc.kit.re3data_-_registry_of_research_data_repositories
- Zenodo: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/eosc.openaire.0a02f13310296033694acead588a773b>

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- PsychArchives:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/eosc.zpid.b96341f00ca4c3a314abcc07fc0084b2>

Did you use any other resources (data, publications, software, training, etc.) provided by the [EOSC resource catalogue](#)?

LIST with bullets the used EOSC resources here (please provide links). *

- FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines:
<https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/search/publication?pid=10.15497%2Frda00050>
- CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025:
<https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/search/other?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.7051012>
- DataCite Best Practice Guide:
<https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/search/publication?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.3559799>

Did you use the [User Dashboard](#) in the EOSC portal?

Please provide feedback. *

We did not use the User Dashboard in the EOSC portal but we plan to do so in the near future to organize the EOSC services and resources we used in this project, alongside other records of interest that would be useful for future REPOPSI development, into an EOSC Marketplace Project.

Did you consult any training resources or sessions about EOSC or provided by the [EOSC Knowledge Hub](#)?

LIST with bullets the used EOSC trainings here (please provide links). *

- For EOSC Providers - Onboarding: <https://openplato.eu/blocks/catalog/detail.php?id=34>
- For EOSC Providers - How to integrate your service with the EOSC Helpdesk?:
<https://openplato.eu/blocks/catalog/detail.php?id=45>
- For EOSC Providers - EOSC Monitoring Service:
<https://openplato.eu/blocks/catalog/detail.php?id=46>

Are you a service provider or do you represent a service provider? If so, did you onboard your [service in EOSC](#) via the providers hub?

LIST with bullets your services in the EOSC catalogue here (please provide links). *

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- We registered our institution as a new EOSC Provider:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/providers/eosc.ubfzf>
- We onboarded the Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/eosc.ubfzf.repopsi>

Did you use or provide to [07InfraEOSC-horizontal service](#) or projects (e.g. [EGI Notebooks](#) or [B2Share](#))?

LIST with bullets the services and/or projects here (please provide links); describe your involvement in 1-2 sentences.

Did you publish datasets or other outputs via the [EOSC portal](#) in one of the listed repositories or in another [registered repository](#)?

LIST with bullets the used EOSC service here (please provide a link to your publication). *

- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/repopsi-rda/>
- Open Science Framework: <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>
- re3data: <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013441>
- FAIRsharing: <https://fairsharing.org/4918>

Did you profit from or contribute to EOSC recommendations or [guidelines](#) provided by [EOSC Task Forces](#) other EOSC bodies?

LIST recommendations or guidelines here (please provide links). Please indicate your participation or profit in 1-2 sentences.

Please, indicate any other output or activity of your project that is linked to EOSC.

LIST with bullets (please provide links). *

- We participated in the EOSC Future and RDA satellite event “Building blocks of Global Research Commons: Europe and beyond”, which was part of RDA’s 20th Plenary in Gothenburg, Sweden:
<https://eoscfuture.eu/eventsfuture/rda-eosc-future-satellite-event-building-blocks-of-global-research-commons-europe-and-beyond>
 - The slides of the lightning talk given at the “The glue to a successful Commons: Interoperability” session are at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7787007>
- We submitted the EOSC in Practice Story: (will be available at)
<https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-in-practice/stories>

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3. RDA Relevant Interactions and Outputs

Are you engaged in [RDA IG or WG](#) or other RDA related contexts?

LIST with bullets your RDA connection, etc. here (please provide links). *

- The project team are all members of the RDA and have joined several RDA IGs and WGs. We plan to contribute to some of the Interest or National RDA groups (e.g. RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG; RDA in South Eastern Europe) in the future.

Did you use or contribute to any [RDA recommendations](#)?

LIST with bullets the recommendations here (please provide links). *

We used the following outputs and recommendations:

- “FAIR Data Maturity Model: Specification and Guidelines (1.0)” by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group: <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>
- “CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements v01.00 2023-2025” by the CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051011>
- “FAIRsharing Standards, Repositories and Policies: facilitating discovery, adoption and use” - Executive Summary of the Adopted Recommendation of the joint RDA-Force11 FAIRsharing Working Group: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fairsharing-registry-connecting-data-policies-standards-and-databases-rda-wg/outcomes>

Please, indicate any other output or activity of your project that is linked to RDA.

LIST here (please provide links). *

We produced four reports as a result of REPOPSI’s self-assessment tests using RDA outputs and recommendations, at the start and at the end of the project:

- REPOPSI Start-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535023>
- REPOPSI Preliminary Start-Project Evaluation Using the CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535052>
- REPOPSI End-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8189262>
- REPOPSI End-Project Evaluation Using the CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8200102>

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Four members of the project team attended RDA's 20th Plenary in Gothenburg, Sweden:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-participant-list>

We participated in the EOSC Future and RDA satellite event "Building blocks of Global Research Commons: Europe and beyond", which was part of RDA's 20th Plenary:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/galvanising-commons-building-global-bridges-commons-and-disciplines>

- The slides of the lightning talk given at the "The glue to a successful Commons: Interoperability" session are at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7787007>

4. Other Outreach activities/events

Did you participate in any outreach activities? If you collected the information already in one of the provided spreadsheets, feel free to copy and paste here. *

We promoted the project outputs on social media in both English and Serbian, primarily via our Laboratory's social media accounts but also via our personal accounts.

Grant award announcement;

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/lira-lab-bgd_reposi-openscience-openaccess-activity-7011683708596293632-VQ6t
- https://twitter.com/LiraLab_Bgd/status/1605922850279489537
- <https://www.facebook.com/LiraLab.Bgd/posts/pfbid02UfFr2HgVFCKnRbktrbPcX5NHGKLGJkrf8SJ79U1RDXdpg3Fk1xPmWeAcuXHTbf8Kl>
- <https://mastodon.social/@alelazic/109557759830204611>

Promotion of the REPOPSI Start-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Report

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/alelazic_reposi-fairdata-openscience-activity-7023342772438847488-Kgtg
- <https://twitter.com/AleLazic/status/1617585893501542402>
- <https://mastodon.social/@alelazic/109739937037477955>

Promotion of our participation at the RDA Plenary

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/lira-lab-bgd_reposi-eoscatrda-rdaplenary-activity-7064964340851875840-52eM
- https://twitter.com/LiraLab_Bgd/status/1659196584192778240
- <https://www.facebook.com/LiraLab.Bgd/posts/pfbid0bi1EMqkbiNLjot4q5q5NP6m1saXA2huDm6euPKm3HcaYQJECfde9aVedXXLbyYk3l>

Invitation to the REPOPSI online workshop

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/lira-lab-bgd_reposi-oscs-otvorenanauka-activity-7075140128888823808-A7IY
- https://twitter.com/LiraLab_Bgd/status/1669378795961188353

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- <https://www.facebook.com/LiraLab.Bgd/posts/pfbid0Hc5ehcza2WuYmiSK1aFBwnbhB3H9SNX7j52cgfSpRjVqrry4dupHJa1rNZGGKiBXI>

Promoting the resources from the REPOPSI online workshop

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/lira-lab-bgd_repospi-repospi-oscs-activity-7079101474118451200-ufcj
- <https://twitter.com/AleLazic/status/1672306729046949888>
- <https://www.facebook.com/LiraLab.Bgd/posts/pfbid035hm7cssj6mUM2PQVH4fJJUutCyDtulhYDT8TepNB1hCkqNmR8wNYFQrkO6T14zenl>
- <https://mastodon.social/@alelazic/110595090765675822>

Public launch of the REPOPSI interactive search app

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/lira-lab-bgd_repospi-openscience-activity-7090320453604405249-ZVIH
- <https://www.facebook.com/LiraLab.Bgd/videos/949966582753846/>
- https://twitter.com/LiraLab_Bgd/status/1684558396366946305
- <https://mastodon.social/@alelazic/110786402371509381>

We organized an online workshop in Serbian titled "REPOPSI 2.0: The project of improving the technology and interoperability of an open repository for psychological instruments" (on June 21, 2023), with the support of the Open Science Community Serbia:

<https://oscs.open.ac.rs/index.php/kategorije/10-kategorije/321-radionica-repospi2>

- Workshop slides and recording are available at:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8071878>

5. Impact, benefits and key messages

What are the impact and the benefits of your project (activities/outcomes, etc.) for scientists, citizen scientists, government bodies and industries, and the public? Please describe the main benefits obtained using the (EOSC) resources. What are the key messages that describe the achievements of your working group best? *

Building new Repository technologies achieved increased user-friendliness, as well as increased sustainability, findability, and interoperability. Because of this, REPOPSI is now even more beneficial to its target user community (i.e. psychology researchers and students). The new website ensures that all important information is more transparently declared and more easily accessed by the users. The new online form makes the contribution procedure more efficient, leaving less room for omissions and errors on the users' part. The new search web app improves the discoverability of Repository's (meta)data, while providing the users with an additional, quick and easy, way to search REPOPSI. Furthermore, putting REPOPSI metadata values into file types (XML) and metadata schemas which are machine-readable and suitable for long-term preservation, improved the Repository's findability, interoperability, and reusability.

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Trustworthy and FAIR research data repositories are an essential part of a country's Open Science landscape. Furthermore, the project efforts focused on diversifying the potential pool of psychological instruments for REPOPSI relied on existing Open Science infrastructures in Serbia (i.e. the E-theses repository). Improving REPOPSI, therefore, ties into Serbia's Open Science Platform but also directly aligns with the EOSC vision to enable scientific communities and research infrastructures towards FAIR management and reliable reuse of research data produced along the research life cycle.

We demonstrated how EOSC resources and RDA recommendations can be leveraged to improve the TRUST-worthiness and FAIR-ness of a community-led open digital repository for psychological research instruments. Our project can, therefore, benefit other providers, especially in the domain of social sciences, who wish to use EOSC resources and RDA recommendations or to develop other smaller-scale open repositories of existing research data. REPOPSI's structure and documentation as well as REPOPSI project deliverables are all public and transparent and available in English, so that they are easily used, transferred or replicated. More locally, the project widened EOSC engagement and RDA recommendations adoption in an institution based in South-Eastern Europe through, among other activities, social media promotion, workshop organization, and the training of junior student assistants involved in project realization.

The main benefit of using EOSC resources is the increased visibility of the REPOPSI repository and the project deliverables. Including REPOPSI in the EOSC Portal and Marketplace and other recognized registries allows us to promote our services to a wider and more diverse pool of potential users. Since REPOPSI project deliverables (e.g. reports, training materials, open-source code) are deposited in Zenodo, they can all also be accessed from EOSC. Thanks to its presence in the EOSC Portal and Marketplace, REPOPSI is able to demonstrate that its services meet EOSC quality standards, expanding its reach and impact in the global community.

The key messages that describe the achievements of our project team are:

- We built new technologies to improve REPOPSI's user focus, sustainability, findability, and interoperability.
- We self-evaluated our progress towards a more TRUST-worthy Repository and more FAIR (meta)data.
- We increased the visibility and impact of project outputs and REPOPSI by including them into the EOSC Portal and Marketplace as well as registered repositories.
- We engaged the REPOPSI target user community and promoted further EOSC and RDA adoption through webinars, social media posts, and blogs.
- We brainstormed and exchanged lessons learned at the RDA Plenary meeting.

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- We diversified the potential pool of psychological instruments by searching less traditional data sources (doctoral theses), moving away from relying solely on contributions from individual researchers and students, which made the process more proactive and efficient.

6. Recommendations and lessons learnt (optional)

Do you have any recommendations for potential users of the EOSC resources you used? What challenges did you face during your project (regarding scientific, technical, research or business challenges)? Could you summarise lessons learnt for other colleagues? *

We recommend that colleagues conducting similar projects communicate with their institutions as early as possible, establish a proper plan for risk mitigation in advance, and think about possible ways to track future activities and outputs stemming from the funded project, even after the official project completion.

7. Travel expenses

Please list your travel expenses, if applicable. *

Travel expenses in the total amount of around 6,500.00 EUR (before taxes) were spent on airplane tickets, hotel lodging, daily allowances, and conference registrations fees so that four members of the REPOPSI project team could attend the RDA 20th Plenary in Gothenburg, Sweden (March 20-23, 2023).

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